

THE STAGES OF PROGRESSING MODERN TECHNOLOGY**Saparniyazova Margarita Ayniyazovna***Lecturer of KSU*

Resume The thesis is about product of the scientific and technical revolution, and the level of development of technology is an indicator of the scientific and technical development of society.

Key words Technique, modern, devices, industry, manufacture, component.

The technique is developed and improved as a result of engineering activities. The design and manufacture of technical devices depends on the type of technical device, the customer's requirements for its technical characteristics (performance, reliability, economy, durability, etc.), quality, cost, manufacturing technology, as well as on the financial and technical capabilities of the manufacturer. Thus, the product or unit may be manufactured industrially while the units are typically assembled from components at the site of operation of the unit. At the same time, individual components of the plant - individual products, units and units - can have high factory readiness and modularity, which significantly reduces the labor and time spent on their integration into the plant and replacement in case of failure. Interchangeability plays a huge role in technology, which reduces costs and facilitates the design, manufacture, operation, maintenance and repair of technical devices.

Modern technology is a product of the scientific and technical revolution, and the level of development of technology is an indicator of the scientific and technical development of society. In a globalizing global economy, advanced technology is spreading rapidly around the world. At the same time, its use in a single country or part of it depends on many factors affecting the availability of equipment and the effectiveness of its practical use - for example, the level of economic development,

market, credit and financial system, the availability and capacity of infrastructure, purchasing power, and the qualifications of users of equipment.

The main purpose of the technique is to rid a person of performing physically difficult or routine (monotonous) work in order to provide him with more time for creative activities, to facilitate his daily life. Various technical devices make it possible to significantly increase labor efficiency and productivity, more efficiently use natural resources, as well as reduce the likelihood of human error when performing any complex operations. The tasks of the technique: Creation of material and cultural values. Production, conversion and transfer of different types of energy. Collection, processing and transmission of information. Creation and use of various means of transportation. Maintaining defense capability.

Currently, mainly equipment is classified by field of application, for example: industrial equipment, transport (Aviation equipment), household appliances, computing equipment, construction equipment, road equipment, etc. Additionally, equipment can be divided into production, for example, machines, tools, measuring means, etc., and non-production - household appliances, passenger vehicles, leisure equipment. A separate class is also military equipment, which includes all technical devices and vehicles designed to maintain defense capability and conduct hostilities on land, at sea, in the air and in space. The technique gradually developed and became more complicated with the development of human society and intelligence. In the era of the Neolithic revolution, agricultural engineering, transport and hydraulic structures, as well as the simplest mechanical devices - a lever, wedge, gate, block, wheel - appeared in the arsenal of human technical devices. Quite a high level of technology reached during the period of Antiquity. Heron wrote not only treatises that describe many of the mechanisms then used, but also the first essay on automata. A water clock, a water organ, a military machine in which compressed air played the role of an elastic body. From the point of view of development, science and technology are very strongly connected. And if in ancient times the development of technology took place mainly on the basis of experience

(empirically), now this is happening on the slice of new scientific knowledge and research, as a result of fundamental discoveries. A prerequisite for the creation of devices such as a nuclear reactor or a modern computer is a deep study of the physical, chemical and other processes underlying their work. On the other hand, scientific research is no longer possible without modern technology of the highest level, in these areas the most advanced developments are always used, for example, the Large Hadron Collider. Thus, the synchronous development of technology and science is an indispensable condition for the movement of human civilization along the technology path chosen by it. And, although this path is sometimes criticized, there are currently no alternatives to it. Over the past centuries, technology has had a decisive impact on the socio-economic structure of human society. It was machine production that caused the transition from feudal society to modern capitalism, and the development of household and consumer technology created modern Western civilization. Progress in military equipment, especially in the field of means of mass destruction, has radically changed the way wars are fought, making large-scale clashes of the world's leading states unlikely. And at present, the development of the so-called "non-lethal" types of weapons is also in full swing, the widespread use of which can significantly change the strategy and tactics of future wars. If we consider the development of technology from the positive side, then in recent years the development of new industries and directions requires tremendous capital and intellectual costs. This leads to wide international cooperation, for example, in the field of space, basic physical research, energy. Modern technologies have become an integral part of the life of not only an individual, but of the whole society as a whole. Now it is quite difficult to imagine an enterprise that would not use the achievements of modern technological progress.

The main task of modern scientific technologies is the introduction of innovative, effective solutions in the development of all spheres of human activity, from the everyday life of everyone to the introduction of developments in industrial production, the agricultural sector and business promotion. In the development of

modern technologies, a special role is assigned to the creation and improvement of so-called renewable energy sources. In addition, the main areas of modern scientific technologies include the creation of various biotechnologies, the development of medicine and pharmaceuticals. As modern information and communication systems, satellite communications are actively used, which equip new models of cars. They are capable of transmitting video and audio signals about possible natural disasters and other natural disasters.

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